

THE DIFFERENCES AND SIMILARITIES OF CASE CATEGORIES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

D. Yarqulova ¹, G. Yo'ldosheva ²

Abstract:

This article contributes to explicate the differences and similarities of case categories in English and Uzbek languages. The reader will notice that the two orientations have various differences, but they have control over language, which highlights the importance of cases between them.

Key words: case, modifiers, nominative, accusative, dative, possessive, subjective.

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A grammatical case is a category of nouns and noun modifiers (determiners, adjectives, participles, and numerals), which corresponds to one or more potential grammatical functions for a nominal group in a wording. In various languages, nominal groups consisting of a noun and its modifiers belong to one of a few such categories. For instance, in English, one says I see them and they see me: the nominative pronouns I/they represent the perceiver and the accusative pronouns me/them represent the phenomenon perceived. Here, nominative and accusative are cases, that is, categories of pronouns corresponding to the functions they have in representation.

English has largely lost its inflected case system but personal pronouns still have three cases, which are simplified forms of the nominative, accusative and genitive cases. They are used with personal pronouns: subjective case (I, you, he, she, it, we, they, who, whoever), objective case (me, you, him, her, it, us, them, whom, whomever) and possessive case (my, mine; your, yours; his; her, hers; its; our, ours; their, theirs; whose; whomever). Forms such as I, he and we are used for the subject ("I kicked the ball"), and forms such as me, him and us are used for the object ("John kicked me").

As a language evolves, cases can merge (for instance, in Ancient Greek, the locative case merged with the dative case), a phenomenon officially called syncretism. Languages such as Latin, Tamil, Russian and German have extensive case systems, with nouns, pronouns, adjectives, and determiners all inflecting (usually by means of different suffixes) to indicate their case. The number of cases differs between languages: Persian has two; modern English has three but for pronouns only; Torlakian dialects, Classical and Modern Standard Arabic have three; German, Icelandic, Modern Greek, and Irish have four; Romanian and Ancient Greek have five; Bengali, Latin, Russian, Slovak, Slovenian, and Turkish each have at least six; Armenian, Czech, Georgian, Kajkavian, Latvian, Lithuanian, Polish, Serbian, Croatian and Ukrainian have seven; Mongolian, Sanskrit, Tamil, and Greenlandic have eight; Assamese has 10; Basque has 13; Estonian has 14; Finnish has 15; Hungarian has 18 and Tsez has 64 cases.

¹ *Yarqulova Dilnoza Mehriddinovna, Teacher of SamSIFL*

² *Yo'ldosheva G. A., Student of SamSIFL*

Commonly encountered cases include nominative, accusative, dative and genitive. A role that one of those languages marks by case is often marked in English with a preposition. For example, the English prepositional phrase with (his) foot (as in "John kicked the ball with his foot") might be rendered in Russian using a single noun in the instrumental case, or in Ancient Greek as τῷ ποδί (tôi podí, meaning "the foot") with both words (the definite article, and the noun ποῦς (pous) "foot") changing to dative form.

More formally, case has been defined as "a system of marking dependent nouns for the type of relationship they bear to their heads". Cases should be distinguished from thematic roles such as agent and patient. They are often closely related, and in languages such as Latin, several thematic roles are realised by a somewhat fixed case for deponent verbs, but cases are a syntagmatic/phrasal category, and thematic roles are the function of a syntagma/phrase in a larger structure. Languages having cases often exhibit free word order, as thematic roles are not required to be marked by position in the sentence. The concept of case in English involves the relationship of a noun, a pronoun, or an adjective (also referred to as a determiner) with other parts of a sentence. The reference form (more technically, the least marked) of certain parts of speech is normally in the nominative case, but that is often not a complete specification of the reference form, as the number and the gender may need to be specified. Thus, the reference or least marked form of an adjective might be the nominative masculine singular.

The parts of speech that are often declined and therefore may have a nominative case are nouns, adjectives, pronouns and (less frequently) numerals and participles. The nominative case often indicates the subject of a verb but sometimes does not indicate any particular relationship with the other parts of a sentence. In some languages, the nominative case is unmarked, and it may then be said to be marked by a null morpheme. Moreover, in most languages with a nominative case, the nominative form is the lemma; that is, it is the reference form used to cite a word, to list it as a dictionary entry etc. There are two types of cases in English. They are nominative and possessive cases, while in Uzbek languages there are six types of it. And they can be used to connect the words with each other. As a result, word combinations will appear and the word can be used as any kind of part of sentence. The system of grammatical forms indicating the syntactic relations of nouns (or pronouns) is usually treated as the category of case. Case is the inflected form of the noun, indicates the grammatical relation in which the noun stands to other parts of the sentence. The problem of the category of case has always been much debated and has become one of the vexed problems of the theoretical discussion. There are a lot of opinions according to the category of case in the Uzbek and English languages. That's why this question is problematic. Generally, there are six main cases in Uzbek language: nominative, accusative, genitive, dative, locative and ablative. Case suffixes are attached to the end of the noun phrase. The nominative case remains unmarked. In the Uzbek language genitive case is expressed by the case ending suffix-ning. The accusative case is expressed by means of the case ending -ni, locative case denotes the place of the thing or a person in the space and is expressed by the ending-da, dative case denotes the direction of an action performed by the subject of the sentence and expressed by means of the case ending -ga, ablative case denotes the beginning point of the action denoted by the verb and expressed by means of the case ending -dan.

In English language most prepositions can perform the function of cases, but there are no prepositions in Uzbek, so as cases are so crucial to connect word phrases and sentences with each other.

Nominative cases are found in Albanian, Arabic, Estonian, Sanskrit, Slovak, Ukrainian, Hungarian, Lithuanian, Georgian, German, Latin, Greek, Icelandic, Old English, Old

French, Polish, Serbian, Czech, Romanian, Russian and Pashto, among other languages. English still retains some nominative pronouns, which are contrasted with the accusative (comparable to the oblique or disjunctive in some other languages): I (accusative me), we (accusative us), he (accusative him), she (accusative her), they (accusative them) and who (accusative whom). A usage that is archaic in most current English dialects is the singular second-person pronoun thou (accusative thee). A special case is the word you: originally, ye was its nominative form and you the accusative, but over time, you has come to be used for the nominative as well. The term "nominative case" is most properly used in the discussion of nominative–accusative languages, such as Latin, Greek and most modern Western European languages.

In active–stative languages, there is a case, sometimes called nominative, that is the most marked case and is used for the subject of a transitive verb or a voluntary subject of an intransitive verb but not for an involuntary subject of an intransitive verb. Since such languages are a relatively new field of study, there is no standard name for this case.

Subjective case

English is now often described as having a subjective case, instead of a nominative, to draw attention to the differences between the "standard" generic nominative and the way that it is used in English.[6][7][8][9][10] The term objective case is then used for the oblique case, which covers the roles of accusative, dative and objects of a preposition. The genitive case is then usually called the possessive form, rather than a noun case per se. English is then said to have two cases: the subjective and the objective.

Examples

Subject

The nominative case marks the subject of a verb. When the verb is active, the nominative is the person or thing doing the action (agent); when the verb is passive, the nominative is the person or thing receiving the action.

The boy saw her.

She was seen by the boy.

Predicate noun or adjective

In copular sentences, the nominative is used for both subject and predicate.

Socrates was a wise man.

Socrates was wise.

The possessive case often conveys possession or ownership, such as Joseph's book or my opinion. It is the only case in which nouns alter their form (e.g., Joseph to Joseph's). This simple alteration changes a person, place, or thing into an owner or possessor of something else.

The possessive case does not always express straight possession or ownership. It also provides information such as origin or authorship (Mozart's music: the music by Mozart), measurement (mile's distance: the distance of a mile), description (children's book: the book for children), and source (report's content: the content of or from the report).

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